

INNOVATION METHODS OF MANAGEMENT IN THE EDUCATIONAL SYSTEM CURRENT

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Abstract: This The article presents several innovative methods of management , including economic methods of management, organizational command method of management, and socio-psychological methods of management .

Key words: Subject of general management , management object, management methods, organizational order, socio-psychological and economic method

Enter. Today, it is known that there are actual problems with the management of educational organizations. In order to improve the quality of education, attention must first be focused on the system. One of the main reasons for the emergence of management problems in education is the rapid changes in society and economy. In short, being stuck with the old management system in modern conditions is one of the main and biggest problems. Today requires us to adopt new management methods.

Management methods are the methods of purpose-oriented influence of the management entity on the management object, that is, ensuring the coordination of the manager's activities in the process of achieving the goals set for the production team he manages.

With the help of management methods, economic processes and production participants are affected in order to achieve high results by spending as little as possible material, financial, energy, and labor resources. Production efficiency is closely related to the perfection and proper formation of management methods.

Management methods occupy an important place in the science of management and are inextricably linked with the laws and principles of management. Among the methods of influencing the labor team, only those that comply with the requirements of the objective laws of management for the management mechanism in the conditions of the market economy are considered the most appropriate and appropriate . The essence of this is that management methods are inextricably linked with the system of laws belonging to the market economy.

Management methods change under the influence of external and internal factors. External factors include: changes in external and internal conditions, implementation of fundamental reforms in the management of the economy, changes in the management system of the level of technical armament of the national economy (economic reforms, transition from the network system of the economy to the regional system, etc.). Internal factors include : implementation of production concentration based on the organization of large production associations; its transfer from one group to another as a result of a change in the size of the enterprise; change in the level of production specialization; improvement of the level of labor supply with equipment; it is possible to improve the existing methods of production planning and rapid regulation and introduce new ones (network planning and management;

continuous rapid production planning, use of an automated production management system, etc.).

Management methods, which directly affect socio-economic relations, change with the development of the production method and the growth of the productive forces of society. Choosing the right management methods is also important for the successful development of the economy.

Management methods can be distinguished as a common phenomenon between different ways of acting in certain specific areas of the economy. For example, it is possible to talk about management methods by management levels (methods of state sector management, shop, enterprise, association, regional management methods), or methods of branch management (methods of industry, transport, agriculture management). It is also possible to distinguish the management methods used by different entities. State management methods, public organization management methods. Or, it is necessary to take into account the management methods used in some areas of the economy (production, financial sector, science and education management methods).

The following methods are used in the management of the national economy: economic, organizational, social, psychological and legal. These methods of management are interdependent, so giving too much importance to any one of them will lead to disruption of the normal course of production as a whole. In the present period, the economic methods of managing the market economy are gaining importance.

Economic methods of management

Economic methods of management influence people through economic interests.

The essence of economic methods is to create economic conditions for employees and the production team, which will ensure their benefit. Economic methods occupy a leading place in the system of management methods.

Economic methods consist of a set of economic influence tools (price, credit, business plan, profit, taxes, wages, economic incentives, etc.), i.e., each team is suitable for influencing economic activity. It consists of activities that ensure that it is implemented in an organic relationship with the joint.

Thus, economic methods of management have very wide possibilities , and good results can be achieved if they are skillfully and timely combined with organizational-command, social-psychological and legal methods.

Enterprises , shareholder societies , companies important management methods one is business plans . It is economical processes nationwide interests looking at the economy in practice objective economic from laws use based on , conscious respectively , one to the goal aspired to without of management mutually organic depends from the system consists of

Business plan by means of solution to be done main tasks of the following consists of : economy development directions and goals done increase ways showing , of the economy stable , proportionate growth provision , material , labor and financial resources networks and work releases in the middle distribution and again distribution , science and technology development achievements current to reach provide ; cross-industry integration , network inside specialization and industry cooperation deepening ; economy host subjects activities fast in order put and coordination to do

Business plan enterprise , shareholders society , concerns of activity everyone sides : product work release and sell _ material and technical supply and work release funds use ,

labor and the work right , in the team social processes and x. k cover takes _ Market relations conditions to them planning about wide rights is given

Management organizational order method

Economy organizations work release manage according to activity of management different organizational order methods apply with depends . Management organizational order methods manager and managed systems efficient activity conduct provider effect reach from the system consists of Management organizational order methods economic methods filling the market economy laws . Legal acts account get and to perform is based on

What because of of management administrative order methods administrative forms with adding take will go That's a lot cases organizational effect administrative the right application , that is decision and orders done to increase is based on But , " management organizational order method » concept « administrative management from the concept of "method " . one so much is wide because organizational order methods of management different to levels different in scope and in the form organizational effect to reach learning cover the issues takes _ Organizational order methods organizational accuracy they provide , external system , each of management joint duties set gives , management apparatus discipline and activity efficiency provides , at work order establishes , decides , f armours performs personnel _ chooses and place- to place puts and xk Management organizational order methods their work to the producers effect reach sources and directions according to to species is separated . It depends without effect of reaching organizational order methods three to the group divided into : organizational-stabilizing , command and discipline _

Impact of reaching order methods restrictive in the documents in the eye not caught there is from the situation come came out without diary fast manage in order to is used . Order of influence main purpose management of the device sure action , management all division and services stable work providing from giving consists of Impact of reaching order methods command , order , instruction and another normative documents based on done is increased .

Command is _ of the leader hand under from employees known task to perform written or oral respectively alb is in doing . Command only linear management system leader by is given Order - from the staff some work release and economy issues solution to demand . _ Order chief deputies , services chiefs , they have has been powers within is given Management in practice applied effect to do methods one is oral is an instruction . Impact to do methods one is oral is an instruction . Impact of reaching such shape all level leaders , but most of the time lower level commanders , brigade bosses , masters they use

Order by means of effect reach perform deadlines with difference does _ command and orders long or short in term intended will be

Socio-psychological methods of management

Socio-psychological methods of management are means of management by influencing the producer and certain individuals on their social needs and psychological characteristics. Application of socio-psychological methods of management, in-depth study of social phenomena occurring in the enterprise requires knowledge of psychological (spiritual) factors affecting the mood of the nervous system of employees.

In production conditions, sociology studies the labor factors that are the basis of the formation of social relations of people, studies social systems, including the laws of development and operation of the production system, the laws of the behavior of people in

different layers of society. social psychology studies the characteristics of group and mass psychology, their influence on the mind and behavior of the individual, factors that stimulate people's activities, mood, factors that shape social thought. Personality psychology studies the types of higher nervous activity and human temperament, character, individual will, ability, character, memory, understanding and feeling, labor psychology studies work activities, including leaders and specialists (professional characteristics and abilities, personnel training learning methods, work and rest schedule, personnel selection and evaluation methods, psychological aspects of the labor process).

Methods of social regulation are used to regulate and harmonize social relations by identifying and aligning the goals and interests of different groups and individuals.

Among them are the regulations of social organizations, contracts, mutual obligations, the selection and distribution of workers and the system of meeting social needs. Methods of social regulation are also used in order to increase the activity of the human factor and democratize management.

Psychological methods of management are aimed at regulating relations between people by creating an optimal psychological state in the team. Psychological methods include the organization of small groups and teams, humanization of work, selection of qualified personnel and their training, etc.

The mental characteristics of a person cannot be understood separately in human activity, because the characteristics of a person's abilities and verbs are manifested in his activity and behavior. A person's life and public activities shape his mental state. It is impossible to realize that a person was born without knowing how to lead a life, what he is doing, that he has developed abilities for this or that thing, and that his actions have been formed.

Man first of all himself creative person as evaluates . Worker to labor such point of view from the point of view to look at immediately does not come : material needs primary they are _ satisfied after relatively high human needs before is pushed .

Man activity known encouraging to factors based on is known _ to the goal to reach is directed . Stimulating the factor is the goal relationship a person activity is the core . General in a sense encouraging factor is _ a person activity conduct for exclamation point factor is the goal while a person him done increase as a result to achieve wanted is something . Stimulating factor person your behavior internal is power . In psychology long and short encouraging factor is separated . If a person activities encouraging factor and own forward put the goal near to the future intended if , it is short term , if they long perspective cover if possible long term is called Stimulating factor level with of a person to work , achievement and to failure relatively has been relationship organic depends . Only long term encouraging factor to labor creative in relation to be is the source

Person spiritual It is a performer of features the work requirements suitable not coming own from the profession dissatisfaction him to try to change , error to do probability to increase and As a result work productivity to decrease take is coming .. on the contrary , if a person own ability complete manifestation do it receiver the work with the waist if so , it is his from labor satisfied will be , the profession fast occupies and work productivity high will be Man for only material incentive consider important _ wrong . To him very a lot thing big common at work own contribution that there is nice to achieve , oneself work through manifestation to achieve , own qualification with pride , comrades in honor of deserves to be

and x's are also important . The majority people personal to prosperity others at the expense of achieved personal success through not the country economy added work at the expense of reach that it is necessary they emphasize .

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